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INFLUENCE OF PARENT'S EDUCATION ON HOME ENVIRONMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to examine how parent's education of high school students influences their home environment. The study analyzed the numerical data from a survey of 300 high school students of Tenkasi Educational District. The investigator used simple random sampling method. Home Environment scale (2017) by the investigator is applied. The data collected is subjected to statistical analysis namely Chi-square test. The findings from chi-square analysis revealed that there is significant association between home environment and father's education of high school students. And also there is significant association between home environment and mother's education of high school students.

Introduction

The term "home environment" refers to all the objects, forces and conditions in the home which influence the child physically. Different home environments vary in many aspects such as the parents' level of education, economic status; occupational status, religious background, attitudes, values, interests, parents expectation for their children, and family size among others, children coming from different home environments are affected differently by such variations. Home Environment is an external factor and parents-students relations is an internal factor. The parents should try to provide healthy environment in the home because children spend most of their time in home. Children take up the ideals and traditions of the social group in which they live. Hence a proper social environment that children express their interest likes and positive attitudes. A proper, rational, healthy, atmosphere, atmosphere in the home enables the child to develop rational habits and rational attitude towards society. Home-interaction may be influenced by educational aspects of families. Parents have the responsibility of getting their children to school in a condition where they are most ready to learn. It also means sending them to school physically and mentally ready to learn. The parents in the home should support their children by listening to them, talking with them about the loss, and acknowledging their feelings. The short-term counseling from the educated parents may be helpful for them. The environment within the family offers special learning conditions for the child and can thus positively improve the development at all levels. Highly educated parents can use their social capital to promote their children's development. A cohesive social network of well-educated individuals socializes their children to expect that they too will attain high levels of academic success. It can also transmit cultural capital by teaching children the specific behaviors, patterns of speech, and cultural references that are valued by the educational and professional elite.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out whether there is any significant association between home environment and Father's Education of high school students.
- To find out whether there is any significant association between home environment and Mother's Education of high school students.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There is no significant association between home environment and Father's Education of high school students.
- There is no significant association between home environment and Mother's Education of high school students.

Principal

S. Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education, Puliangudi

Methodology

Survey method of investigation is employed for the study. A total sample of 300 high school students is drawn from the population using simple random sampling technique to respond to the instrument for data collection for the study. The sample consisted of 300 high school students in the schools of Tenkasi Educational District. Home Environment scale is developed and standardized by the investigator (2017). The data collected is subjected to statistical analysis namely Chi-square test.

Analysis of Data

Null Hypothesis: *There is no significant association between home environment and Father's Education of high school students.*

Table 1
Chi-Square Test showing the Significant Association between Home Environment and Father's Education of High School Students

Variable	Background Variable	Category	df	Calculated χ^2 -value	Table value	Remarks
Home environment	Father's education	Illiterate	4	30.474	9.488	S
		School Education				
		College Education				

S - Significant at 5% level of significance

It is inferred from the above that the calculated 'chi-square' value (30.474) is greater than the table (9.488) for df (4) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant association between home environment and father's education of high school students.

Null Hypothesis: *There is no significant association between home environment and Mother's Education of high school students.*

Table 2
Chi-Square Test Showing the Significant Association between Home Environment and Mother's Education of High School Students

Variable	Background Variable	Category	df	Calculated χ^2 -value	Table value	Remarks
Home environment	Mother's Education	Illiterate	4	39.766	9.488	S
		School Education				
		College Education				

S - Significant at 5% level of significance

It is inferred from the above that the calculated 'chi-square' value (39.766) is greater than the table (9.488) for df (4) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant association between home environment and mother's education of high school students.

Findings of the Study

- There is significant association between home environment and Father's Education of high school students.
- There is significant association between home environment and Mother's Education of high school students.

Interpretation and Conclusion

The findings from chi-square analysis revealed that there is significant association between home environment and father's education of high school students. And also there is significant association between home environment and mother's education of high school students. The findings highlighted the

importance of parents' education in the enhancement of the home environment of the high school students. And also it revealed that parents' education of high school students has an important influence on the home environment they create for their children, and it is a predictor of cognitive and behavioral outcomes.

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